

Advancing Open Research Information – Insights from the National Open Access Irish Monitor

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Purpose

This abstract examines the development and implementation of the National Open Access Monitor, Ireland (OpenAIRE, 2023), a tool designed to evaluate Ireland's progress in adopting Open Research Information practices as outlined in the National Action Plan for Open Research 2022–2030 (NORF, 2022). By leveraging data from the OpenAIRE Graph (Manghi et al, 2022) the National Open Access Monitor, Ireland provides evidence-based insights into policy compliance, research practices, and institutional performance. The Monitor addresses the needs of policymakers, funders, institutions and their repositories, and researchers, offering a comprehensive framework for tracking and understanding the implementation of Open Research Information policies.

Ireland's National Action Plan (NORF, 2022) places a strong emphasis on embedding the principles of open research, including the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), into the national research ecosystem. The Monitor plays a pivotal role in assessing the impact of these policies, fostering transparency, and supporting the equitable dissemination of research outputs.

Policy Context

The National Action Plan for Open Research 2022–2030 (NORF, 2022) is a cornerstone of Ireland's efforts to promote Open Research Information practices. The Plan outlines three core objectives: achieving 100% Open Access to publicly funded research outputs, fostering a culture of openness and collaboration, and embedding FAIR principles into the management of research data and outputs. These goals align with international frameworks such as UNESCO's Recommendation on Open Science (UNESCO, 2021) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2016).

The Plan also emphasizes the importance of evidence-based, public evaluation tools for assessing policy implementation and guiding strategic interventions. The Irish National Open Access Monitor has been developed in response to this need, providing policymakers and stakeholders with data-driven insights to track compliance, identify gaps, and refine strategies (Ferris, C., 2022). The Monitor's integration with the OpenAIRE Graph ensures that these

insights are based on comprehensive and interoperable metadata, aligning Ireland's open research ecosystem with global standards.

In addition to supporting national objectives, the Monitor reflects Ireland's commitment to international collaboration on Open Research Information. In this context, the Monitor is fully aligned with the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information and with the commitments of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). Openness of research information is at its core, ensuring that assessment practices are transparent, inclusive, and based on auditable evidence. The Monitor supports a shift away from journal-based metrics toward a broader recognition of research contributions, reinforcing CoARA's principles of responsible and qualitative evaluation and enhancing the coverage and diversity of outputs. By enabling detailed analyses of open access practices, it contributes to the global effort to promote transparency, inclusivity, and equitable access to research outputs.

Methods

The Irish National Open Access Monitor aggregates metadata from the OpenAIRE Graph (OpenAIRE Non-Profit Civil Partnership, & Lempesis, A. 2024), an open scholarly communication database that collects and harmonizes data from over 2,200 sources, including institutional repositories, thematic repositories, and large-scale aggregators. Following a stakeholders' consultation (Ferris, C., 2023), the Monitor evaluates Open Research Information practices across five key dimensions:

1. National Trends: Tracks compliance with open access mandates and identifies patterns in research accessibility.
2. Research Performing Organizations (RPOs): Benchmarks institutional contributions and supports strategy refinement.
3. Research Funding Organizations (RFOs): Evaluates the impact of funding mandates on Open Research Information outcomes.
4. Researchers: Highlights individual contributions to Open Research Information, promoting accountability and recognition.
5. Institutional Repositories: Assesses repositories' roles in preserving and disseminating research outputs, identifying gaps and areas for improvement.

The Monitor integrates data from the OpenAIRE Graph's relational database, which includes approximately 193 million publications, 73.5 million datasets, 600,000 software records, and 24 million other outputs. Interactive tools embedded within the Monitor enable stakeholders to visualize, customize, and download data for their specific needs. These tools are designed to provide not only quantitative metrics but also qualitative insights into how policies, training initiatives, and funding strategies influence research practices over time.

Results

The Irish National Open Access Monitor delivers a detailed analysis of Ireland's Open Research Information landscape (Grypari, I., 2023). At the national level, it tracks trends in compliance with open access mandates, highlighting disparities across disciplines, institutions, and funding bodies. Policymakers use these insights to evaluate the effectiveness of open research initiatives and prioritize interventions.

For Research Performing Organizations (RPOs), the Monitor facilitates benchmarking by comparing institutional contributions to Open Research Information. These comparisons support strategy development and help institutions align their practices with national and global objectives. Research Funding Organizations (RFOs) benefit from the Monitor's ability to link funding mandates to research outputs, offering evidence of policy effectiveness and identifying areas for improvement.

The Monitor also highlights individual researchers' contributions, promoting accountability and recognizing efforts to align with Open Research Information principles. At the repository level, it evaluates institutional repositories for their roles in ensuring the accessibility and preservation of research outputs. Insights gained through the Monitor support the development of strategies to enhance repository performance and integration into Ireland's broader Open Research Information framework.

Interactive features embedded within the Monitor allow stakeholders to explore and adapt data for their unique contexts. For example, policymakers can use visualized national trends to assess policy compliance, while institutional managers may focus on benchmarking tools to refine organizational strategies.

Value

The National Open Access Irish Monitor represents a significant advancement in the evaluation and promotion of Open Research Information practices. By leveraging data from the OpenAIRE Graph and integrating interactive tools, it offers stakeholders actionable insights into research practices, policy compliance, and areas for improvement.

This initiative supports the objectives of the National Action Plan for Open Research 2022–2030, which emphasizes achieving 100% open access to publicly funded research outputs and embedding FAIR principles into the national research ecosystem. The Monitor contributes to this vision by providing a robust, evidence-based framework for tracking progress and understanding how policies influence research practices over time.

A key feature of the Monitor is its focus on collaboration and capacity building. OpenAIRE has actively engaged with Irish stakeholders through training sessions, metadata improvement efforts, and one-on-one consultations, fostering a culture of openness and shared responsibility. This collaborative approach ensures that the Monitor remains responsive to the needs of its diverse users, from policymakers and funders to researchers and institutional managers.

The broader implications of the Monitor extend beyond Ireland. By demonstrating how Open Research Information practices can be evaluated through robust metadata aggregation and interactive tools, this case study offers a replicable model for other countries or regions seeking to monitor and promote open research. Its alignment with international frameworks highlights its relevance within the global context of Open Science.

Challenges and Future Directions

The development and implementation of the Irish National Open Access Monitor revealed challenges such as metadata inconsistencies, incomplete records, and variability in compliance across disciplines and institutions (Manghi P, 2024). To address these issues,

OpenAIRE collaborated with Irish stakeholders to improve metadata quality through deduplication sprints, targeted training, and tailored support (Gypari I et al, 2024).

Balancing quantitative metrics with meaningful, context-sensitive insights was another challenge. The Monitor was designed to go beyond static metrics, offering stakeholders tools to explore how policies, funding strategies, and training activities influence the adoption of Open Research Information. This ensures that the Monitor remains adaptable to the evolving needs of Ireland's research ecosystem.

Looking ahead, the Monitor will continue to play a critical role in guiding Ireland's transition to open research. Its findings will inform adjustments to policies, the allocation of resources, and capacity-building initiatives. Planned enhancements to the OpenAIRE Graph, such as the integration of person entities and taxonomies aligned with Fields of Science (FoS) and United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), will further support the Monitor's ability to evaluate Open Research Information practices.

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